

Reaction of boro collections to blast disease. G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, U. P., India.

Reaction	Collections	
	(no.)	(% of total)
Highly resistant	0	0.0
Resistant	5	5.6
Mod. resistant	5	5.6
Mod. susceptible	4	4.5
Susceptible	7	7.8
Very susceptible	14	15.6
Highly susceptible	55	60.9

8, and 31 have white kernels and UPRB-32 and 33 have red kernels. UPRB-8 and UPRB-32 have slender grains; UPRB-33 and 8 have short, bold grains. UPRB-31 is also resistant to cold temperature and to bacterial blight; it is being used as a donor parent. All the resistant and moderately resistant collections need to be tested against other stresses.

Varietal reaction to brown spot and narrow leaf spot under natural infection

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Two fungus diseases – brown spot, caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Hann, and narrow leaf spot, caused by *Cercospora oryzae* Miyake – were observed in the northeastern, central, and southern ricegrowing areas of Thailand. Chantharasnit and Aroonskul reported that RD1, RD2, and RD3 were resistant to brown spot under glasshouse conditions and artificial inoculation. Many multiple-resistant lines from the cross BKN 6517-63-4-3/RD9 recently exhibited high susceptibility to brown spot at the heading stage. We suspect that brown spot will become a major disease in the future. Therefore, we tested many breeding lines in the seedling stage for reaction to brown spot and narrow leaf spot under natural infection.

We tested 464 breeding lines from the intrastation and interstation yield trials in the 1975 wet season at the seedling stage under natural infection at the Kuan Gut Rice Experiment Station and the Ubolrajthani Rice Experiment Station. RD1 and Khao Dawk Mali 105 were

used as resistant and susceptible checks, respectively. The test rows were surrounded by two rows of Hang Yi 71 to keep high moisture among the plants. No fertilizer or other chemicals were applied. The reactions of rice plants to brown spot and to narrow leaf spot,

Varieties and lines found to be resistant to brown spot and narrow brown leaf spot.

Designation	Cross	Resistance rating ^a	
		Brown spot	Narrow leaf spot
SPT 6606-100	LT82/Sigadis	R	MR
UBN 6721-5-39-3(1)	IR262A/NSPT	MR	MR
BKN 6721-11-8-4-1	IR262A/NSPT ²	R	MR
KKN 6721-5-7-4	IR262A/NSPT ²	R	MR
SPT 66064-2-1-1	LT82/Sigadis	R	MR
SPT 6606-6-1-1-1	LT82/Sigadis	MR	MR
SPT 6606-36-1-1-1	LT82/Sigadis	MR	MR
SPT 6012-97	GR201/LY34	MR	MR
KDML'65 G ₄ U-4-351	Irr. KDML 105	MR	MR
KDML'65 G ₄ U-4-522	Irr. KDML 105	R	MR
KDML'65 G ₁ U-45	Irr. KDML 105	MR	MR
SKN 24	KDML 105/F16216	MR	R
SKN 48	KDML 105/F16216	MR	MR
SKN 15	KDML 105/F16216	MR	MR
SKN 49	KDML 105/F16216	MR	MR
SPT'58-37-389	DML 70 ² /Chinese 345	MR	MR
SPT'58-37-400	DML 70 ² /Chinese 345	MR	MR
SPT 6207-297	Pin Gaew Bow 27/JL 11	R	R
BKN 323-17	KTH 17/Ramadja	MR	MR
492-2-204	Khao Gaew	MR	MR
KTH'65-G ₂ U-31	Irr. KTH 17	MR	MR
KTH'65-G ₁ U-67	Irr. KTH 17	MR	R
SPRC'70-11-32	Leuang Hawm	MR	MR
SPRC'70-12-45	Khao Pra Juab	MR	MR
SPT 6838-2-1-1	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-76-2-2-1	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-87-2-1-4	SPT 662467/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-96-1-1-1	SPT 662467/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-125-1-1-2	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	R
SPT 6838-94-1-1-4	SPT 6624-67/NSPT	MR	MR
SPT 6838-86-2-2-1	SPT 662467/NSPT	MR	R
BKN 7130-511	Short Sigadis/KPM 148	MR	MR
SPT 6840-10-2-2-4	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	MR
SPT 6840-80-2-1-2	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	R
SPT 6840-82-2-1-1	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	R
SPT 6840-82-2-1-3	NSPT/SPT 6624-67	MR	MR
SPT 6840-51-2-2-1	NSPT/SPT 662467	MR	MR
	NPY 70	MR	MR
	NSPT	MR	MR

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

based on the number of lesions, were recorded at 45 days after seeding: less than 1% lesions, highly resistant; 1–576 lesions, moderately resistant; 5–25% lesions, intermediate; 25–50% lesions, moderately susceptible; and more than 50% lesions, highly susceptible.

Only 8 percent were resistant to brown spot and 4 percent to narrow leaf spot. The lines that were resistant to both diseases are shown in the accompanying table. RD1 and Khao Dawk Mali 105 were classified as intermediate and moderately susceptible, respectively. Infection of brown spot fungus was severe at both the Kuan Gut and the Ubolrajthani Rice Experiment Stations, but narrow leaf spot infection was severe only at Kuan Gut.

Direct and indirect effect of Udbatta disease on total number of panicles per hill in different paddy cultures

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Udbatta disease caused by *Ephelis oryzae* Syd. is one of the important paddy diseases in Karnataka. Affected plants show profuse tillering early in plant growth, whitening of young leaves, nonproductive panicles, panicles in the form of cylindrical rods, or a few diseased and healthy panicles in the same clump. Reporting on the direct loss from the disease, Shivanandappa said that wherever the primary tiller was infected, the percentage of infection within the hill ranged from 20 to 95 percent. But when infection took place on the secondary and tertiary tillers, the percentage of diseased panicles varied from 13 to 55 percent. The indirect loss from the disease in terms of reduction in total number of productive panicles in the affected hill is not known. Hence the following study was conducted.

Twenty short- and 20 medium-duration rices were selected and sown in kharif 1974 at Mandya in randomized block

Effect of Udbatta disease on the total number of panicles per hill. Rice Research Station, Mandya, and Department of Plant Pathology, UAS, Hebbal, Bangalore, India.

Variety or culture	Disease incidence (%)	Healthy panicles (no.)		Panicles per diseased hill (no.)	Diseased panicles (no.)		
		Per healthy hill	Per diseased hill		Per diseased hill	Indirectly lost	Total lost
<i>Short-duration cultures</i>							
MR 118	8.25	10.52	7.64	9.89	2.25	0.63	2.88
MR 263	4.24	12.02	8.33	10.02	1.69	2.00	3.69
MR 272	4.76	14.08	10.68	12.12	1.44	1.96	3.40
MR 279	4.54	13.28	11.52	12.92	1.40	0.36	1.76
MR 297	5.60	8.56	6.45	8.26	1.81	0.30	2.11
MR 298	5.21	9.60	7.32	9.21	1.89	0.39	2.28
MR 299	4.96	9.41	6.96	8.64	1.68	0.77	2.45
MR 300	2.41	8.88	6.12	7.77	1.65	1.11	2.76
MR 301	4.96	10.41	7.94	9.83	1.89	0.58	2.47
MR 318	2.44	8.77	6.12	8.02	1.90	0.75	2.65
IET 1522	3.89	9.45	6.04	7.82	1.78	1.63	3.41
IET 1899	2.06	10.26	6.60	8.29	1.69	1.97	3.66
IET 1988	2.73	10.73	8.52	10.13	1.61	0.60	2.21
IET 2246	2.93	8.77	6.37	7.87	1.50	0.90	2.40
IET 2386	2.28	11.25	8.26	9.86	1.60	1.39	2.99
IET 2671	3.94	9.64	6.85	8.55	1.70	1.09	2.79
IET 2707	3.44	10.50	8.30	10.20	1.90	0.30	2.20
IET 2968	4.60	11.20	7.73	9.53	1.80	1.67	3.47
IET 3126	4.99	10.85	7.80	9.80	2.00	1.05	3.05
Madhu	4.70	11.29	8.42	10.38	1.96	0.91	2.87
<i>Medium-duration cultures</i>							
MR 44	6.30	14.85	11.96	14.29	2.33	0.56	2.89
MR 70	5.06	14.26	11.28	13.34	2.06	0.92	2.98
MR 81	5.00	12.80	10.37	12.44	2.07	0.36	2.43
MR 249	4.38	14.80	12.70	14.40	1.70	0.40	2.10
MR 269	3.84	11.60	9.11	10.99	1.88	0.61	2.49
GMR 2	4.76	11.01	7.43	9.38	1.95	1.63	3.58
Satya	3.60	11.16	7.78	9.54	1.76	1.62	3.38
Surya	3.53	12.36	10.11	11.86	1.75	0.50	2.25
Suhasini	5.17	12.20	8.65	10.83	2.18	1.37	3.55
Jaya	4.69	11.45	8.46	10.57	2.11	0.88	2.99
IR20	4.18	11.73	9.08	11.14	2.06	0.59	2.65
J.H. 49	3.53	8.85	6.68	8.36	1.68	0.49	2.17
IET 1990	4.31	11.65	8.60	10.53	1.93	1.12	3.05
IET 1991	3.26	11.58	8.88	10.83	1.95	0.75	2.91
IET 2142	4.69	11.36	8.45	10.61	2.16	0.75	2.91
IET 2143	3.80	13.83	11.41	13.19	1.78	0.64	2.42
IET 2254	3.87	12.46	9.86	11.79	1.93	0.67	2.60
IET 2295	2.92	14.60	12.85	14.36	1.51	0.24	1.75
IET 2300	6.15	11.73	8.36	10.27	1.91	1.46	3.37
IET 2384	3.87	13.55	10.56	12.39	1.83	1.16	2.99

design with three replications. Twenty-five healthy and diseased hills of each culture were randomly selected in each replication. The healthy and diseased panicles at grain formation in healthy and diseased hills were counted. The number of diseased panicles in diseased hills (direct loss) was obtained by counting the affected panicles in each diseased hill. The indirect loss of panicles was obtained by deducting the total number of panicles (healthy and diseased) in diseased hills from the total number of healthy panicles in healthy

hills. The total loss of panicles was calculated as both direct and indirect loss (see table).

The percentage of disease incidence varied from culture to culture. There was no correlation between the percentage of incidence and the direct or indirect loss of panicles. The range of indirect loss of panicles from culture to culture varied greatly. The number of directly lost panicles per hill ranged from 1.40 to 2.33; that of the indirectly lost ranged from 0.3 to 2.00. Total lost panicles ranged from 1.75 to 3.69.